

REFORMATION OF EDUCATIONAL ASSESSMENT IN NIGERIA: A PANACEA FOR ACHIEVING SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS (SDG)

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Abstract

Assessment forms a very purposeful tool for making decision regarding these components of education, school and learning that are highlighted. It is for this reason that any reformation initiative that is planned for improvement in education, must give prime of place to assessment, if education must achieve its developmental goals and objectives, and be sustained. This paper explores the assessment practices particularly the school-based or continuous assessment practices in Nigerian schools as a central theme of the emerging goals and policies in education globally. The paper identifies gaps in the current educational assessment, and posits that as a relational term with schooling and learning, the extent to which assessment exerts its driving force in determining the future of the other two, and sustainability in educational development, obviously depends on the effectiveness of implementation of assessment practices at the classrooms, schools and national levels, as directed by appropriate educational policies. The paper also presents theoretical frameworks and empirical evidences for assessment in the reform system and concludes that if the targets of the emerging goals and policies (especially in education) which majorly address the achievement of sustainable development goals are to be met, then the current policies and practices in assessment should respond to these reforms or changes.

Key words: Education, Educational Assessment, Reformation, SDGs and Nigeria

Introduction

Education is an indispensable social component and a powerful tool to develop a peaceful and sustainable society. Global policy frame works are coupled with national policy frameworks to facilitate strategic use of education to promote sustainability (Cars and West, 2015). It is widely agreed that education is the most effective means that any society possesses for confronting the challenges of the future. Indeed education will shape the world of tomorrow.

Education is said to change the learner's behaviour desirably, and the quantity and quality of such changes are often determined by assessment. This puts assessment at the centre of every effort of the education process. Consequently, any serious reform initiative that is meant to bring improvement in education must necessarily give assessment a prime of place. Educational

assessment refers to the process of collecting information for decision making in education about students, schools, curricular, programmes and policies (Afemikhe, 2015). Assessment involves the quantity and quality of all the inputs and processes involved in education as well as their outcomes. It is through assessment that the definition of education is achieved, the monitoring of its processes and the documentation of its products.

Assessment within the Nigerian educational context has attempted to approximate the goals of learning and schooling through the formulation of policies. A policy is said to be valid to the extent that inputs into its formulation are valid. Since assessment forms a major source of input into the formulation of educational policy, it is imperative that scores arrived at through

assessment practices, be made valid for effective and valid decision making.

Good quality measurements are a necessity for better decision making, but do not guarantee excellent decisions. Assessment is *sine quo non* for determining goal attainment. It is an interpretation that is based on internal standard of measurement results in an attempt to ascertain the level and value of progress made or changes observed (Joshua 2005). In other words, it is assessment that determines the changes that are desired. The quantity and quality of the 'change' and how much 'change' is acceptable for one to be said to have 'learned' is determined by evaluation and together with feedback from assessment enhances teaching and learning (Nenty, 2015). Therefore, educational assessment is the totality of processes involved in making valid judgment about what behavioral characteristics and changes a learner has acquired through the process of teaching and learning. It is integral to educational process. Within the school, assessment is a crucial process in placing or choosing students into programmes, highlighting their strengths and weaknesses in the learning process, and determining those who qualify and are worthy of certificates. Hence, assessments include those for improvement (Assessment for learning (AFL)) and those for certificates (Assessment of learning (AOL)) which have been technically referred to as formative and summative assessments respectively.

An aspect of assessment which is executed by and within the school from the perspective of the authorities but not of learners plays an important role of determining who gets admitted or selected into educational programmes, monitoring the components of the educational system to see how students are performing and tries to diagnose any problem hindering the optimal performances of both the students and the school. The assessment information provides useful tools to hold accountable, those responsible for the different components of the school system in an effort to achieve its goals. Thus, the integrity of the entire educational system depends, to a large extent on the quality of its assessment

practices. Therefore, any need for policy reforms in education will automatically call for reviews or changes in the policies and practices of educational assessment. This paper aims to examine assessment practices in Nigeria with the hope to expose areas of needed reform for effective practices for development and sustainability.

Issues of Policy and Assessment Practices in Nigeria

Assessment is a process which involves the collection of meaningful information for decision making. The results from assessment are major drivers of policy formulation and implementation especially in developed countries (Pohjola & Tuomisto, 2011), and also constitute the pillar which sustains educational decision from the classroom (lowest) to government levels. Therefore, the way assessment is carried out right from the primary school level contributes to the quality of education at the national level.

Assessments provide means for democratizing policy-making processes especially, as they involve the participation by, and inputs from a good number of stakeholders including teachers, students, parents, community and government agencies. As inputs into education policy formulation come majorly from assessments; it is imperative that such inputs be valid in order to ensure the formulation of valid policy. Thus, we should ensure that the scores we arrive at through assessment are valid measurement of the characteristics of interest. If this is the case, then the question of the implementation of most educational policies not yielding solution to the problem for which the policies were formulated due to the quality of input or information from assessment, would not arise.

Assessment gathers and analyses data with which to infer an individual's standing on particular traits. The data collected on individuals are to help describe, understand, and make them better. When assessment is conducted at the school level, it is regarded as internal or school-based assessment. It involves how teachers get information on the performance, understanding, and behaviour of

learners. School-based assessment also constitutes how information is interpreted and used to improve teaching and learning, and taking relevant decisions about students, curriculum, instruction and educational policies. In Nigeria, school-based assessment comprises continuous assessment (CA) and end of term/semester examinations which account for 30 percent and 70 percent of the total score respectively at the senior secondary and tertiary levels of education. At the primary school and junior secondary levels, the ratio of CA to end of term examination is 40:60 respectively.

The National Policy on Education (1998:7) revised (2008) has emphasized the need to adopt CA practices in varying degrees as described above into the various levels of education in Nigeria. But the main purpose of this paper is to examine how reforms in educational assessment can help achieve the goals of education and their sustainability. CA has continued to be seen and approached particularly in terms of implementation as a new method of assessment in Nigeria. But development in some other parts of the world tends to confirm that CA has been a well-known mode of assessment prior to its introduction into Nigerian educational system. Existing literature tends to view CA as being concerned with "when" and "how" of assessment rather than being a new method on its own (Hassan, 2015). It can then be regarded as an error, any attempt to raise CA to the status of a technique in its own right. Despite the position or view held about CA, it has become a pivot upon which the current National Policy on Education stands. Therefore, the need to bring reforms into the areas of this assessment practice where such changes are needed to bring effectiveness into the assessment practices and sustainable educational development.

Continuous assessment is a household word in the Nigerian school system (Joshua, 2005). Teachers at all levels of schools all over the country are expected to carry out the continuous assessment of their students. Every school registering students for public graduating examination including West African Senior and Junior School Certificate

Examinations and National Examination Council prepares the continuous assessment scores of students for submission to the examination body and agency or ministry for the Junior and Senior Secondary School graduating examinations.

CA is a policy matter as the NPE specifies that 'educational assessment and evaluation will be liberalized by basing them wholly or in part, on continuous assessment' (FRN, 1998:7). Furthermore, paragraphs 1, 5, 23, 43, 70 and 100 of the same document prescribe CA as an integral part of evaluation at the various levels of education in Nigeria. CA is systematic collection of grades over a period of time and their aggregation into a final grade (Joshua 2005). Through CA, what a student gains from school in terms of knowledge, industry and character development, as measured through tests, assignments, projects and other educational activities in a term, year or during the entire period of education at all levels, are being ascertained. But for long, the bulk of our educational assessment has been narrowed down to written (paper-and-pencil) examinations. In other words, at every stage in the education enterprise, assessment of learning outcomes forms an integral part of the teaching-learning process.

This followed from the introduction of western education into Nigeria about one hundred and sixty years ago. It came with its approach of formalized assessment in form of either oral, written or practical examinations. Thereafter, the written examinations developed and overshadowed the other forms of assessment. The oral examinations became limited to the assessment of infant and higher degree dissertations. And the practical examinations which were meant to assist with the assessment of learning in the sciences and science related subjects (technical) were relegated to the background.

The assessment picture above had hardly taken root within our classroom when external bodies emerged to examine students. Consequently, the teachers of these students were left with nothing to contribute by way of input in the assessment process that is designed to certify the adequacy and appropriateness of

their learning experience. The classroom teachers were therefore confronted with two major challenges. First, the teacher must learn how to carry out classroom assessment of the performance of his students for effective learning gains and for the enhancement of the teaching-learning process. Secondly, the teacher must learn how to tailor his teaching towards preparing students to meet the content and assessment requirements that align with the external examinations but which are alien to his classroom environment. This same situation presented itself both at the primary level where examinations were conducted by regional Ministries of Education, and at the secondary level where external examinations were conducted by an international body—first the Cambridge Examination Matriculation board and later the West African Examination Council which came on board in 1952.

The system of educational assessment described above was fraught with problems. Hassan (2005) enumerated the problems as follows:

- (i) The assessment was usually restricted to only one (cognitive) of the several aspects (domains) of the learner's behaviour.
- (ii) It pushed assessment of learning outcomes to the very end of teaching-learning process.
- (iii) It often proved to be a threat to the learner and the teacher and the curriculum innovators.
- (iv) It did not encourage innovativeness and creativity in the teacher and the learner.
- (v) It promotes poor study habit on the part of the learners as they may prefer preparation for examination to the very end of learning segment.
- (vi) It may not permit the true performance of learners to be determined since results are easily influenced by chance occurrences like sudden illness, luck, etc.
- (vii) It tended to encourage do-or-die disposition from students with the attendant behavior such as examination malpractices in the form of exam leakages, impersonation during tests

and examination, vandalism among others.

- (viii) The results of the examination were hardly communicated to the learner in any meaningful manner.

The above and many other reasons constituted impetus or the justification for the introduction of CA. The CA policy provides that, the final grading of a student in the cognitive, effective and psychomotor domains of knowledge, takes into account in a systematic manner all performances of the student during a given period of schooling. This is to be done through continual or series of periodic assessments using tests and non-test measures and yielding records which the school counselor should keep, use, maintain and update. Beside its guidance oriented role, CA implies that what a child does in school right from the first day till his or her last day is put together systematically and cumulatively in order to yield a comprehensive or overall terminal performance of the student. The confidence in the continuous assessment practices is also anchored on the fact that it is based on the true score which encourages multiple measurement. Theoretically, CA of the many measurements that are involved, can reveal the true ability of the learner, as it allows the errors of measurement (error scores) to average themselves to zero. Therefore, the many measurement involved in the CA process constitute a means of getting closer to the true ability of the student. Given the above, the seriousness and carefulness with which assessment procedures are approached and handled, will dictate the validity of the measurement outcomes.

The true picture of educational assessment in Nigeria

The policy thrust upon which educational assessment in Nigeria rests is CA. The CA as the main assessment practices in Nigerian schools today, is still concentrating on cognitive achievement (and lower levels for that matter) to the detriment of the affective and psychomotor development of learners (Ipaye, 1986; Okon, 1986; Iyewarun, 1986; Joshua, 2005 & Afemikhe 2015). This is not

unconnected with the Nigerian Society's quest for paper qualification. Thus, a child with pass marks in his/her subjects, receives a certificate at the end of the course no matter how "bad his/her manners are or how unskilled he/she may be. In other words, behavior, attitude, interest, aptitude and other affective and psychomotor traits do not count towards obtaining a certificate in our system of assessment. This is worrisome and therefore, calls for an urgent review in order to achieve sustainable development in education and national economy as a whole. Educational evaluators and researchers (Okon, 1986; Joshua, 2005; Idowu & Esere, 2009; Ugodulunwa, 1996; Umoinyang, 1996; Umoinyang, Asim, Akwa & Bassey, 2004; Nenty, 2015) have prescribed a departure from this trend to make room for a comprehensive picture of the development of learners in the school system.

According to the Federal Ministry of Education Handbook on CA, the mission of the teacher and the school, should be to balance the learners' development in the three domains such that:

- (i) Much knowledge and understanding is ensured (cognitive)
- (ii) Much desirable interest and attitude (affective) are ensured.
- (iii) Much physical skills (psychomotor) are developed and show cased.

Much changes in habits of thinking, feeling and doing (cognitive, affective and psychomotor) are ensured among learners. Looking at the performance so far of Nigerian education and assessment policies and practices above, it cannot be said that the education enterprise in Nigeria has failed (in terms of policy guidance), the same can hardly be said of the implementation of these policy guidance. Joshua (2005) confirmed that the implementation challenges of continuous assessment have remained:

- 1) Emphasis on cognitive learning.
- 2) No variety in the assessment instrument as most of the continuous assessment practices in our schools centre on paper-and-pencil tests.

- 3) Lack of knowledge and skills in tests and measurement.
- 4) The problem of comparability of standards.

These shortcomings have long been overcome by teachers, administrators and other assessment personnel in advanced countries (Hassan, 2005). For government seeking to reform or improve education quality and achieve sustainable development, a sound reformation in assessment policy and practices is crucial. For school level assessment to be influential, it should be in addition to being comprehensive, consistent, regular, reliable, part of an overall school development policy, diagnostic and reconcile both formative and summative assessments with strong focus on providing constructive feedback and feed forward to learners and teachers. Teachers are at the core of the assessment practices and are expected to be trained as there cannot be any effective teaching and learning without valid, reliable, well-structured and coordinated assessment and evaluation. They are involved in the planning, gathering evidences, interpreting the assessment data and using the results for decision making. They could conduct formative and summative assessments and be encouraged to develop various forms of assessment tasks that are authentic and contextualized, as well as receive encouragement to enhance learners' higher order thinking skills, including the 21st century skills such as creative, innovative, problem solving and decision making, in addition to instilling moral values.

The way forward

Research studies (Hassan, 1987; Ugodulunwa & Musa, 1996; Nenty, 2005) have pointed at teachers' lack of competence in the operation of CA of affective and psychomotor aspects, as a major source of challenge to assessment practice in Nigeria. This is because a teacher who is not proficient in the assessment of the affective and psycho-motor behaviour of students, construction of assessment instrument, validation and interpretation of test scores, as well as data analysis techniques; will definitely be found wanting when it comes to continuous

assessment procedures. Evidently, differences in quality of assessment instrument may bring about differences in the performance of pupils taught the same subjects by different teachers.

Until now, teachers have always been accused of conducting classroom assessment practices that emphasize only lower levels of cognition (Nenty, 2005; Afemkhe, 2015). This is generally inadequate as a means of preparing the learners to fit in and contribute to the development of self and society. With School-Based Assessment (SBA) or Continuous Assessment CA embedded in the teaching and learning process, it could be expected to reduce the fear usually associated with public examinations. And this would lead to the production of good quality students for sustainable educational development. An effective way to achieve further sustainability is by involving teachers in designing lesson objectives that call for higher order cognitive ability and translating them directly into appropriate activities during teaching and assessment. Class, school and even national examinations for which the learners are prepared, should compose of items that are valid and predominantly call for higher rather than lower order skills such as agility, innovation, creativity and problem solving skills-requirement of the 21st century that are embedded in these levels. In their study on primary school teachers' perception of classroom assessment practices as a means of providing quality primary education in Nigeria and Botswana; Nenty, Adedoyin, Odili and Major (2005), found that except for memory level, Nigeria and Botswana primary school teachers' perception of the level to which each of the cognitive behavior is important in enhancing quality of education, fail significantly to inform their classroom assessment practices. In each case, they under performed in their involvement of the relevant type of questions, items and exercises during classroom assessment practices. It could be noted that, this deficit might be as a result of lack of adequate training of teachers in assessment techniques especially in the development of skill at different levels of cognition among learners. To UNESCO

(2005), it also reflects the pressure of external summative assessment on teaching and learning. It is important to note that effective assessments require adequate resources, teachers who are grounded in assessment techniques and relatively small class-size, but that hardly fit the realities in Nigeria and many other developing countries.

Looking at the assessment practice as it obtains in Nigeria schools, Joshua (2005) opined that most of the school teachers and administrators are still relatively blank as far as skill in test construction and interpretation are concerned. Several views on assessment have settled on the issue of implementation as most problematic (Joshua, 2005; Hassan, 2005 & Afemikhe, 2015). Incidentally, an area of assessment implementation where urgent reformation could also be addressed is development and evaluation of assessment instrument and their varied use. The implementation of assessment requires instruments. It is from the assessment instrument that valid and reliable information is yielded for critical decision about individuals, group and organizations. Assessment is a process and involves the collection of meaningful information to understand and help people cope with problems. Developing and validating assessment instrument are often expected to be handled with all amount of expertise and carefulness. The construction of good instrument is painstaking and demands time, commitment and scientific or technical knowhow (Nenty & Umoinyang, 2004). Similarly, Joshua (2005) noted that the validity of information which any assessment instruments provides depends on the care that goes into planning and constructing such instrument. The reformative emphasis in assessment instrument could be viewed along the line of intensifying critical skills in the use of test blue print or table of specification as a necessary aid to ensuring content validity, item analysis, score transformation and item revision. It is a vital requirement for government to rise to the challenge of training and retraining of the implementers-who are the

teachers and administrators, through assessment skills.

When the teachers are trained, the same skill, care and effort that go into the development of achievement intelligence, ability and aptitude tests which are cognitive instruments commonly associated with measurement of learners in our schools, should equally be expected in constructing non-cognitive assessment instruments broadly categorized by Joshua (2005) into observation, peer appraisal and self-report. The different types of instrument required for successful implementation of assessment could be achieved through school team work in different schools.

Also, the ongoing reform in the education sector of Nigeria puts premium on public examination results as the yardstick for determining standards and quality of education delivery in Nigeria. The present assessment practices including the large-scale assessment characterized by high-stakes particularly true for our public examinations (WAEC, NECO, etc) especially as examinees can go to any length to ensure that they pass deserve much attention in the reform initiative. The craze to pass by all means has been noted by Afemikhe (2015) to be the preponderance of irregularities in assessment in Nigeria.

Assessment irregularities involve events which cause assessed performance to deviate from the actual performance. Idika and Joshua (2005) described it as individual's intentional and unfair urge to get a score higher than what his ability and honest effort in the subject would have otherwise enabled him. An effective reform agenda aimed at stamping out this, and attend to other security issues arising from valid e-assessment delivery will constitute vital agenda for reform in education. It is only when assessment of students (AOL or AFL) takes place with a particular student taking the assessment, that we can have confidence in the assessment information which is generated. With paper-and-pencil assessment, shortcomings have been noted, and this is why many suggestions for control have been pointed out (Idika, 2015; Nwogwugwu, Ovat & Idika, 2016).

According to Stecher (2012), the much interest in assessment with particular emphasis still on test is as a result of the effects on students, teachers and principals, parents, policy makers, judgment about programme performance and allocation of resources. Tests could prompt schools to reform policy, encourage teachers to adopt more effective practices and motivate students to learn. It is also possible one could expect changes in policy making reform and goals from such assessment, to determine the extent to which changes in behavior due to gained score are indicative of improvement in learning or assessment.

Although assessment has been used greatly as highlighted above, its use by policy makers has notably been limited (Spillane, 2005), despite their responsibilities towards decision making for which assessment inputs, Chuderwood, Zapata-Rwera and Van Winkle (2010) clearly indicated policy makers' role in decision making to include; school improvement plans that focus on information about students' strengths and weaknesses, goals and community pressure. Others are professional development, programme selection, improvement of students' achievement, staff allocation and communication. All said, the gains of high stakes assessment (alongside the challenge of cheating, teaching to the test, limited sample of behaviour being measured leading to sampling error, reliability, validity issues; basing decision on a single score and consideration of non-instructional variable that impact negatively on achievement, include providing more instructional time, working harder to cover more materials within a given time, and working more effectively. In all, the data derived from high-stakes assessment can be seen to be useful to policy makers for assessing schools and system-level performance. Therefore, large-scale assessment as practiced by our public examinations may only be a source of worry when it serves a high-stake function. Otherwise, thinking towards making large-scale assessment more effective is a move in the right direction.

Issues of educational assessment, sustainable development goals (SDGs) and reforms required in Nigeria

The Federal Ministry of Education (FME) through its relevant agencies is making concerted efforts to improve reliability of national examination systems in the assessment of candidates' academic performance. This development, if accompanied by reform in educational assessment, is probably appropriate as it is in tune with the trend worldwide (Afemikhe, 2007). As part of the global effort by education authorities to facilitate strategic use of policies in education to promote sustainability, universal sustainable development agenda with transformative ambitions were presented due to the short comings of the MDGs. The development agenda referred to as sustainable development goals (SDGs) consist of seventeen goals as proposed by the Open Working Group as a Post 2015 agenda.

According to the overview of the SDGs, the goal four as proposed by the Open Working Group (OWG) (Loewe & Ripping, 2015), states "ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote life-long learning opportunities for all". A general assessment of the goal is about ensuring inclusive and equitable quality education and promoting life-long opportunities for all. Unlike the MDGs, it focuses predominantly on educational/learning outcomes and cognitive skills rather than school attendance and enrolment, thereby taking into serious consideration the commendations made in recent years by the Education For All (EFA) initiative and new empirical research. Furthermore the goals include seven targets and three suggestions as means of implementation with the first target which requires that by 2030, "ensure that all girls and boys complete free, equitable and quality primary and secondary education leading to relevant and effective learning outcomes". The target will ensure that every individual is provided with access to education and the relevant and effective learning outcomes can

be generated through effective and efficient assessment procedures. Hence, it is important that relevant reforms in educational assessment be done to achieve this sustainable development educationally.

Ultimately, sustainable development will require an education that not only continues throughout life, but is also as broad as life itself; an education that serves all people, draws upon all domains of knowledge and seeks to integrate learning into all of life's major activities. According to UNESCO (2002), education for sustainable development emphasizes a holistic, interdisciplinary approach to develop the knowledge and skills as well as changes in values, behaviour, and lifestyles, and empower everyone, young and old, to make decisions and act in culturally appropriate and locally relevant ways to redress the problems that threaten our common future. Sustainable development is a dynamic concept that utilizes all aspect of public awareness, education and training to create or enhance an understanding of the linkages among the issues of sustainable development. It addresses learning skills, perspectives, and values that guide and motivate people to seek sustainable livelihoods, participate in a democratic society, and live in a sustainable manner. It also involves studying local and when appropriate, global issues. It gives opportunity for every person to benefit from educational opportunities and to learn the lifestyles, behaviours and values necessary to create a sustainable future. It is a vision of education that seeks to balance human and economic well-being with the earth's natural resources. This vision of education helps students to better understand the world in which they live, addressing the complexity and interconnectedness of problems such as poverty, wasteful consumption, environmental degradation, urban decay, population growth, gender inequality, health conflict and the violation of human rights that threaten our future and also seeks to empower people to assume responsibilities for creating a sustainable society. An assessment reform initiative that can address this nature of learning experiences is what the nation needs

to compete favourably with its counterparts, in settings where an enhanced assessment practices are prioritized.

In spite of the considerable progress which has been made, there are still enormous barriers of reorientation of formal education to sustainability; barriers that cannot be addressed by the efforts of individual teachers or even schools, no matter how committed they might be. Effectively overcoming such barriers required commitment by society as a whole to sustainable development. Such commitment would involve all of society's stakeholders to work collaboratively and in partnership, including industry, business, grassroots organizations and members of the public, to develop policies and processes which integrate social, economic, cultural, political and conservation goals (UNESCO, 1997). A sustainable society will be one in which all aspects of civic and personal lives are compatible with sustainable development, and governments at all levels must work together to advance such a society. The role of formal education in building society is to help students to determine what is best to conserve in their cultural, economic and natural heritage and to nurture values and strategies for attaining sustainability in their local communities while contributing at the same time to national and global goals.

The issue of educational assessment cannot be separated from sustainable development in Nigeria, as it helps to evaluate all the facet of education. According to UNESCO (1997), reorienting the curriculum towards sustainable development requires at least two major structural reforms in education. The first to re-examine the centralized mandating of courses and textbooks in order to allow for locally relevant learning programmes. Local decision-making can be facilitated through the reform of centralized educational policies and curricula, and the formulation of appropriate syllabuses and assessment policies. National syllabus can serve as broad framework documents which provide aims and general objectives for subjects, an overview of broad content themes, appropriate learning experiences, relevant resources and criteria for assessing student's

learning. This type of syllabus can provide centralized accountability, while allowing schools, teachers and students to make choices about the specific learning experience, the relative depth and breadth of treatment for different topics, the case studies and educational resources used, and how to assess students' achievements.

Another vital area where structural reform can take place leading to sustainable development is the development of new ways to assess the processes and outcomes of learning. Such reform should be inspired by what people want from their educational system, as well as what society needs. The period of profound change in which we are living needs to be taken into account by educational systems, which were, for the most part, designed to serve a society which is fast becoming history. Learning needs to be seen as a lifelong process which empowers people to live useful and productive lives the future needs – this is fundamental for sustainable development, including its ultimate objectives not only of human survival but especially of human well-being and happiness (UNESCO, 1997). Similarly, there's also need of revamping of the methods of credentialing students. The various ways in which students are judged (testing, report card, evaluations) and the basis for awarding diplomas at all levels, need to reflect the reformation of outcomes of learning towards sustainability.

Educational assessment reformations are varied and extremely complex, and certainly cannot be addressed only, or even chiefly, through reformation. However, assessment policy and practices are critical to any successful educational improvement strategy. Assessment data essential to teaching and learning, are needed to monitor, evaluate and improve the educational system. Although some assessments serve learners, teachers, parents and policymakers by providing them with useful information, others focus educational efforts by virtue of the consequences that are attached to learner's performance. In the absence of serious consequences, it is difficult for assessment to exert much influence on an educational system. However, if performance from

assessment entails serious consequences, it can lead to activities that are educationally unproductive and may actually undermine the integrity of the system. Various assessment policies have taken place in Nigeria to bring about development and advancement of the country holistically through education but much impact has not been felt, it is this gap that this paper is intended to fill.

Conclusion

This paper has x-rayed the true picture of assessment practices in Nigerian educational system. The practices were supposed to be school-based or the continuous assessment policy which was in turn to be guided by the relevant provisions in the National Policy on Education. But the reality of the assessment system today is that we have completely deviated from the policy provisions. The policy, however, may seem adequate for the purpose it was intended, but the implementations have been the major challenge. The problems of implementation have been buttressed as the apparent lack of competence on the part of teachers, administrators and other assessment personnel to handle the project. Thus, instead of having the assessment to compliment learning, its handling makes it completely alien to the goal of schooling and learning.

In all these, assessment and education face a conflicting prospect. For education to play its proper role, the assessment component should be reformed with adequate emphasis on the implementation of those aspects particularly the non-cognitives that can hasten our overall development and sustainability. This lies in the proper identification of global and national targets of the emerged and emerging goals and policies particularly in education which strongly bear relevance with the achievement of sustainable development goals and a proper re-examination of national policies and practices in educational assessment. Focusing reform initiatives on these aspects of assessment is simply safeguarding the future of schooling and learning in Nigeria.

Suggestions:

- Skill training and re-training of teachers in the art of continuous assessment and use of assessment techniques
- Balancing of formative and summative assessments in teaching and learning
- Proper monitoring by assessment personnel to ensure validity & reliability of relevant information (decisions) that are fed into educational policy from assessments.
- Adequate resources for effective and efficient assessment of learners.

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